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Kurzfassung

Bei der Entwicklung von Systemen werden häufig modulare Ansätze verwendet um die Wiederverwendbarkeit von Komponenten zu nutzen. Doch selbst wenn sicher ist, dass jede einzelne Komponente korrekt funktioniert, kann das Gesamtsystem aufgrund der komplexen Interaktionen zwischen den Komponenten dennoch unerwartetes Verhalten zeigen. Diese Herausforderung macht deutlich, dass Verifikationstechniken benötigt werden, die über die Verifikation einzelner Komponenten hinausgehen. In dieser Arbeit wird ein generischer Ansatz zur Verifikation von Netzwerken aus IEC 61499 Funktionsblöcken unter Verwendung von Schnittstellenautomaten vorgestellt. Die vorgeschlagene Methode verwendet den Kompositionsformalismus für Schnittstellenautomaten, um eine formale Darstellung des gesamten Netzwerks zu erstellen. Durch den Einsatz dieser Technik können potentielle Fehler in der Kommunikation zwischen den modellierten Funktionsblöcken identifiziert und beseitigt werden, wodurch die Korrektheit des gegebenen Netzwerks effektiv überprüft werden kann. Darüber hinaus führt der Ansatz das Konzept der Erweiterung von Schnittstellenautomaten ein, um das oft gewünschte Verwerfen von ausgegebenen Events zu berücksichtigen, und es an die IEC 61499 Funktionsblöcke anzupassen. Die finale Methode ist als Pseudocode in Algorithmus 3 beschrieben. Um die Wirksamkeit des Ansatzes zu bewerten, wurde er auf ein reales Beispiel, die Capping Station, angewandt, und die Ergebnisse vorgestellt.

Abstract

Systems are often developed using modular approaches to leverage reusability of components. However, even when each component is proven to function correctly, the overall system may still exhibit unexpected behaviour due to the complex interactions between components. This challenge highlights the need for verification techniques that extend beyond individual components. This thesis presents a generic approach to verify networks of IEC 61499 Function Blocks using Interface Automata. The proposed method uses the composition formalism for Interface Automata to create a formal representation of the entire network. By employing this technique, potential errors in communication between the modelled Function Blocks can be identified and eliminated, effectively validating whether the suggested network is valid. Moreover, the approach introduces the concept of extending Interface Automata to account for often desired ignorance of issued events, tailoring it to IEC 61499 Function Blocks. The final method is presented as pseudocode in Algorithm 3. To evaluate the effectiveness of the approach, it was applied to a real-world example, the Capping Station, and the results presented.

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1 Introduction

As modern cyber physical systems are becoming more and more complex, it is crucial to ensure correctness and validity of such systems. Since these systems are often deployed in environments where updating or replacing software is challenging or even impossible, minimising errors at deployment becomes a priority. This depends, among other factors, on which design approach is employed. Although not as successful as in other domains [1], approaches like component-based design are used effectively by the IEC 61499 Standard. It uses Function Blocks as its fundamental components and enables the creation and reuse of them. These Function Blocks can then be connected to form complex networks to control, for example, automation systems. To verify correctness of such networks, one needs a theoretical model to express not only the internal structure and behaviour of the Function Blocks themselves, but also their communication within the networks. In 2001, De Alfaro and Henzinger already proposed a formalism that is very suitable for modelling this, so called Interface Automata [2]. Based on Finite State Automata, Interface Automata can express the internal behaviour of a restricted version of Function Blocks and are especially well suited to model communication between them. Using the original approach of De Alfaro and Henzinger to compose Interface Automata and their notion of error states, this thesis will show that this approach can be used effectively to verify the correctness of networks of Function Blocks.

First work on this has already been done in [3] and [4] in the context of hierarchical automata. In contrast to this thesis, they do not consider general networks of Interface Automata.

1.1 Problem Statement

By using and reusing components instead of developing a system in a monolithic manner, a risk lies in whether or not the network was composed correctly, i.e., the components interact as intended. Ensuring this correctness at deployment is even more important in the context of cyber physical systems.

1.2 Proposed Approach

We employ the basic approach of composing Interface Automata to model the interaction of Function Blocks in a network, given Interface Automata that exhibit the same behaviour as the Function Blocks they model. By correctly handling the arising error states, we will use this for verification of such networks. The resulting verification process is described in Algorithm 3.

1.3 Guideline through the Work

This thesis is structured as follows. First, Chapter 2 will introduce the necessary formalisms and key concepts that will be used in later chapters and form the basis of the analysis. Chapter 3 will cover increasingly complex examples to illustrate the approach, followed by a rigorous proof demonstrating its validity and a more detailed analysis of error handling. The resulting Algorithm 3 concludes the chapter. Chapter 4 will then apply the outlined approach to a real world example. Finally, Chapter 5 summarises and discusses the findings and gives an outlook on future research directions and possible extensions and improvements.

2 Background

2.1 IEC 61499 Standard

The IEC 61499 Standard is a standard for the development of software modules in distributed industrial-process measurement and control systems [5]. Its core concept are so called Function Blocks (FBs) . They describe a functional unit of software of a certain type. An example of an FB *F1* can be seen in Figure 2.1

Figure 2.1: Example of a Function Block *F1*

As seen above, FBs have input and output ports for events and data. In the case of Figure 2.1, the event input ports are *on*, *off*, and *error*, the event output ports are *start* and *stop*, the data input ports are *sizeIn* and *delay*, and the data output port is *sizeOut*. A network of FBs usually consists of many FB instances of certain FB types that are

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connected. The mentioned data and event ports can be used to combine FBs to networks and propagate events and data from one FB to one or more other FBs. Similarly, an FB can receive inputs from one or more FBs. An example of a network of FBs can be seen in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2: Example of a Function Block network

Additionally, data can be associated with certain events. If so, the associated data input ports get updated when the associated event occurs. In this way, FBs can communicate with each other via events and related data, making it possible to model complex behaviour. FBs can also possess internal features, often referred to as encapsulated functionality. This means that each FB can consist of an arbitrary amount of subcomponents that it uses to provide its functionality.

In this thesis, we limit the analysis to the externally observable behaviour of FBs, ignoring any internal processes. This only means that we work on a fixed layer of abstraction and do not consider subcomponents of FBs explicitly. Internal behaviour will occur again when composing a network of FBs and considering a formal representation of the network itself. Furthermore, we will only consider FBs without data connections.

2.2 Interface Automata

In the following sections, the most important formalisms and theoretical concepts that form the basis of this thesis will be introduced. For most definitions, we stick closely to the ones formulated by de Alfaro and Henzinger in [2].

The core concept of this thesis is the so called Interface Automaton (IA). An IA is a finite state machine. It can be visualised as a directed graph with labelled edges called actions. Each state has a set of possible actions that can transition the automaton to a new state.

Figure 2.3: Example of an Interface Automaton depicted as a directed graph

The key aspect of an IA is that it categorises these actions into three distinct sets: input, output, and hidden actions. As seen in Figure 2.3, we will append ? for input, ! for output, and ; for hidden actions to make them visually distinguishable. We will later use those to model input, output, and internal behaviour of FBs. Formally, we define IAs as follows.

Definition 2.2.1. Let $P := (V_P, V_P^{init}, \mathcal{A}_P^I, \mathcal{A}_P^O, \mathcal{A}_P^H, \mathcal{T}_P)$. We call P an Interface Automaton, with V_P being the set of states of P , $V_P^{init} \subseteq V_P$ being a non-empty set of initial states, $\mathcal{A}_P^I, \mathcal{A}_P^O, \mathcal{A}_P^H$ being the sets of input, output, and hidden actions of P respectively, and $\mathcal{T}_P \subseteq V_P \times \mathcal{A}_P \times V_P$ being the set of valid steps in P for $\mathcal{A}_P := (\mathcal{A}_P^I \cup \mathcal{A}_P^O \cup \mathcal{A}_P^H)$.

We will sometimes write $P = (V_P = \{a, b\}, V_P^{init} = \{a\}, \dots)$ to clarify which set in the tuple corresponds to which set of the IA. As seen in the formal definition, not every action

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is accepted in every state. For example in Figure 2.3, the action *in* can only be issued in state 1. This motivates the following definition:

Definition 2.2.2. *We call actions that are accepted by an IA P at a certain state $v \in V_P$ enabled actions and denote them with $\mathcal{A}_P(v)$. Similarly, we write $\mathcal{A}_P^O(v)$ for output, $\mathcal{A}_P^I(v)$ for input, and $\mathcal{A}_P^H(v)$ for hidden actions.*

2.3 Composability

We now introduce the notion of composability of IAs, which is the concept of letting two IAs interact with each other via their input and output actions. This corresponds to viewing them as a network structure where P feeds some or all of its outputs into Q or vice versa. Formally, we allow for input actions of P to be output actions of Q , meaning that Q is feeding its output into P . This applies for all four possible input output pairings of P and Q . Note that we do not allow for any overlap of input or output actions, meaning that if action a is an input action of P , it might be an output action of Q , but it cannot be an input action of Q . The same is true for hidden actions. Formally, we define it as follows.

Definition 2.3.1. *We call two IAs composable if $\mathcal{A}_P^H \cap \mathcal{A}_Q = \mathcal{A}_Q^H \cap \mathcal{A}_P = \emptyset$ and $\mathcal{A}_P^I \cap \mathcal{A}_Q^I = \mathcal{A}_P^O \cap \mathcal{A}_Q^O = \emptyset$.*

From a visual (graph-visualisation) perspective, combining IAs this way might not seem intuitive. If we think about modelling FBs, defining composability this way makes a lot of sense, as will become clear later. From this definition, it can be easily checked if two IAs are composable by evaluating the intersections of the respective set of actions. We now look at what we actually mean by combining two IAs. The first concept we need is the product automaton, which we define as follows.

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Definition 2.3.2. *Let P and Q be IAs. We define their product $P \otimes Q$ as the IA defined by*

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_{P \otimes Q} &= V_P \times V_Q, \\
 V_{P \otimes Q}^{init} &= V_P^{init} \times V_Q^{init}, \\
 \mathcal{A}_{P \otimes Q}^I &= (\mathcal{A}_P^I \cup \mathcal{A}_Q^I) \setminus \mathcal{A}_P \cap \mathcal{A}_Q, \\
 \mathcal{A}_{P \otimes Q}^O &= (\mathcal{A}_P^O \cup \mathcal{A}_Q^O) \setminus \mathcal{A}_P \cap \mathcal{A}_Q, \\
 \mathcal{A}_{P \otimes Q}^H &= \mathcal{A}_P^H \cup \mathcal{A}_Q^H \cup (\mathcal{A}_P \cap \mathcal{A}_Q), \\
 \mathcal{T}_{P \otimes Q} &= \{ ((v, u), a, (v', u)) : (v, a, v') \in \mathcal{T}_P \wedge u \in V_Q \wedge a \notin \mathcal{A}_P \cap \mathcal{A}_Q \} \\
 &\quad \cup \{ ((v, u), a, (v, u')) : (u, a, u') \in \mathcal{T}_Q \wedge v \in V_P \wedge a \notin \mathcal{A}_P \cap \mathcal{A}_Q \} \\
 &\quad \cup \{ ((v, u), a, (v', u')) : (v, a, v') \in \mathcal{T}_P \wedge (u, a, u') \in \mathcal{T}_Q \wedge a \in \mathcal{A}_P \cap \mathcal{A}_Q \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

From this definition, we can see that the product internally keeps track of the states in which the individual IAs are currently in, with each state consisting of only initial states of the individual IAs being an initial state of the product. Note that the input and output actions of the product are stripped of any overlapping actions of the IAs, as those now connect the two IAs internally and are therefore converted to hidden actions. Moreover, if there is a transition in P from a state a to a state b , then there is also a transition in $P \otimes Q$ from the state (a, u) to the state (b, u) for every state $u \in V_Q$ and vice versa for transitions in Q . If the action involved in the transition is present in both IAs and there is also a transition in Q from a state u to a state v , then this transition shows up in the product as a transition from the state (a, u) to the state (b, v) .

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Figure 2.4 shows an example of a simple product for the IAs A and B defined below.

$$\begin{aligned}
 A : \quad & V_A = \{ a, b \}, \\
 & V_A^{\text{init}} = \{ a \}, \\
 & \mathcal{A}_A^I = \{ in \}, \\
 & \mathcal{A}_A^O = \{ link \}, \\
 & \mathcal{A}_A^H = \emptyset, \\
 & \mathcal{T}_A = \{ (a, in, b), (b, link, b) \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 B : \quad & V_B = \{ 1 \}, \\
 & V_B^{\text{init}} = \{ 1 \}, \\
 & \mathcal{A}_B^I = \{ link \}, \\
 & \mathcal{A}_B^O = \emptyset, \\
 & \mathcal{A}_B^H = \emptyset, \\
 & \mathcal{T}_B = \{ (1, link, 1) \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Product} : \quad & V_{A \otimes B} = \{ 1a, 1b \}, \\
 & V_{A \otimes B}^{\text{init}} = \{ 1a \}, \\
 & \mathcal{A}_{A \otimes B}^I = \{ in \}, \\
 & \mathcal{A}_{A \otimes B}^O = \emptyset, \\
 & \mathcal{A}_{A \otimes B}^H = \{ link \}, \\
 & \mathcal{T}_{A \otimes B} = \{ (1a, in, 1b), (1b, link, 1b) \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

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Figure 2.4: Two Interface Automata A and B and their product with a shared action $link$

Note that this is not the composition, but the product. In order to obtain a valid composition, we want to strip the product of its error states. This is similar to asking the question: In which states are the IAs compatible with each other and can states occur in which the network does not act as intended? To find and remove such errors, we first need to define what exactly we mean by error state.

2.4 Error States

The purpose of error states is to highlight whether or not two IAs P and Q are communicating correctly. We define error states as those states in which an output action of P can occur, but Q is currently in a state that does not accept this as an input action, i.e., the action is not an enabled input action at the current state of Q . This can be interpreted as P providing an invalid input to Q . Figure 2.5 show a slightly different version of Figure 2.4 that produces an error state marked in red. In this case, the error state results from $link$ being a shared action and an enabled output action in A , but not an enabled input action in B .

Definition 2.4.1. We define the set of error states of two IAs P and Q by $Illegal(P, Q) := \{ (v, u) \in V_P \times V_Q \mid \exists a \in \mathcal{A}_P \cap \mathcal{A}_Q : a \in \mathcal{A}_P^O(v) \wedge a \notin \mathcal{A}_Q^I(u) \vee a \in \mathcal{A}_Q^O(u) \wedge a \notin \mathcal{A}_P^I(v) \}$.

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Figure 2.5: Product of two Interface Automata *A* and *B* with highlighted error state

If we want to check if two IAs work with each other, we simply compute their product and check if error states are reachable from the initial states. When computing the product of two IAs *P* and *Q*, we obtain one of two results: A closed IA [2], i.e., a product that has neither input nor output actions, or an open IA, which does. For closed IA, the resulting system is closed-off, meaning there is no way to exert influence onto the system from the outside. Because of this, we can simply check if there are error states that are reachable from the initial states.

A downside of this concept is that it defines a binary concept of error states. This has been extended for example by [6]. They use may- and must-transitions to account for different guarantees of the system. With this, one can decide between potential error states, which might still be resolved, and fatal error states that render two systems incompatible. In Section 3.4 we will also look at different types of error states in the context of modelling FB networks.

2.5 Environments

If we do not obtain a closed IA as the product, we can look for an environment that makes the two IAs work together. An environment is another IA that we define as the outermost

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layer that can be thought of as surrounding the network. It provides inputs to the IAs and accepts their outputs. Because the states an open IA can reach depend also on the input it receives, the choice of environment matters.

De Alfaro and Henzinger highlight a key difference in their approach: They define two IAs as compatible if an environment exists in which they can function together - a so called optimistic approach -, contrasting with traditional methods that often take a pessimistic approach, requiring IAs to be compatible in all possible environments. We formally define an environment as follows.

Definition 2.5.1. *Let P and E be IAs. E is an environment of P if*

$$E \text{ is composable with } P, \tag{2.1}$$

$$V_E \neq \emptyset, \tag{2.2}$$

$$\mathcal{A}_E^I = \mathcal{A}_P^O, \text{ and} \tag{2.3}$$

$$\text{Illegal}(P, E) = \emptyset. \tag{2.4}$$

These restrictions ensure that the environment consists of at least an initial state, that it accepts all the outputs of P and that its composition with P does not lead to any error states, i.e., the environment correctly interacts with the IA P . Note that this does not mean that, if P is a composition of multiple IAs, the environment prevents error states in P itself.

We can now take a look at the algorithm from [2] to create a composition of two IAs and formally define what we mean by composition.

2.6 Composition

We define two IAs as compatible if they are non-empty, composable, and there exists an environment that prevents the product IA from entering error states. We define the compatible states of two IAs as follows.

Definition 2.6.1. *Let P and Q be two composable IAs. A pair of states $(u, v) \in V_P \times V_Q$ is called compatible if there exists an environment E s.t. no state in $\text{Illegal}(P, Q) \times E$ is reachable in*

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$(P \otimes Q) \otimes E$ from any state $((u, v), e) \in \{(u, v)\} \times V_E^{init}$. We denote the set of all compatible states of $P \otimes Q$ by $Cmp(P, Q)$.

This means that we consider (u, v) as an intermediate starting state and check if the environment can prevent $P \otimes Q$ from entering error states from there. Two IAs are therefore compatible if their initial states are compatible.

As seen above, if the product of two IAs is closed, specifying an environment does not make sense. Hence, to check compatibility, we form the product and check if any error states are reachable from the initial states. One can do that by either checking for all reachable states whether they are error states or, if all the error states are known, check if those error states are reachable from the given initial states.

If the product is an open IA, then it is not clear which states are reachable, as it also depends on the input given by the environment. It is still possible to check if there exists an environment that makes the two IAs compatible. The idea is to start with the set of error states $Illegal(P, Q)$ of two IAs P and Q and then to identify all states from which those error states can be reached by using only output or hidden actions. If such a state is reached at any point, the environment cannot guarantee that $P \otimes Q$ does not transition to an error state, as it has no control over the output or hidden actions of $P \otimes Q$. Thus, a legal environment must prevent the composition of entering such a state. A legal environment can therefore be designed to not issue certain input actions in certain states that could lead to an error state in $P \otimes Q$.

We will define this notion of backwards-reachability as follows.

Definition 2.6.2. *Let P be an IA. For a set $U \subseteq V_P$, we define*

$$OHpre_P(U) := \{v \in V_P \mid \exists (v, a, u) \in \mathcal{T}_P \wedge a \in \mathcal{A}_P^O \cup \mathcal{A}_P^H\}, \text{ for all } u \in U.$$

With this, we can take a look at the algorithm for computing the compatible states of two IAs.

We can now formally define what we mean by the Composition of two IAs.

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Algorithm 1: Algorithm to compute compatible states of two Interface Automata [2]

Input: Interface Automata P and Q

Output: $Cmp(P, Q)$

$U_0 \leftarrow Illegal(P, Q);$

$k \leftarrow 0;$

repeat

$U_{k+1} \leftarrow U_k \cup OHpre_{P \otimes Q}(U_k);$

until $U_{k+1} == U_k;$

return $V_{P \otimes Q} \setminus U_k;$

Definition 2.6.3. Let P and Q be two composable IAs. We define the composition $P||Q$ to be the IA defined by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_{P||Q} &= Cmp(P, Q), \\
 V_{P||Q}^{init} &= V_{P \otimes Q}^{init} \cap Cmp(P, Q), \\
 \mathcal{A}_{P||Q}^I &= (\mathcal{A}_P^I \cup \mathcal{A}_Q^I) \setminus (\mathcal{A}_P \cap \mathcal{A}_Q), \\
 \mathcal{A}_{P||Q}^O &= (\mathcal{A}_P^O \cup \mathcal{A}_Q^O) \setminus (\mathcal{A}_P \cap \mathcal{A}_Q), \\
 \mathcal{A}_{P||Q}^H &= \mathcal{A}_P^H \cup \mathcal{A}_Q^H \cup (\mathcal{A}_P \cap \mathcal{A}_Q), \\
 \mathcal{T}_{P||Q} &= \mathcal{T}_{P \otimes Q} \cap (Cmp(P, Q) \times \mathcal{A}_{P||Q} \times Cmp(P, Q)).
 \end{aligned}$$

By this definition, the actions of the composition are the same as in the product. The only difference is that we only allow for states that are compatible, i.e., states which cannot lead to error states without an environment being able to prevent it. Because of that, we also have to remove all transitions that do not go from one compatible state to another compatible state.

We call an environment that prohibits the IA from entering error states a legal environment and define it formally as follows.

Definition 2.6.4. Let P and Q be IAs. We call the IA E a legal environment if

E is an environment of $P \otimes Q$, and
no state in $Illegal(P, Q) \times V_E$ is reachable in $(P \otimes Q) \otimes E$.

2.7 Refinement

In order to check whether an IA Q exhibits the same behaviour as another IA P and possibly more, de Alfaro and Henzinger introduce the notion of refinement. This is specifically useful to check whether or not an IA can be replaced by another one. In order to formally define this, we need a few definitions first. We start by looking at states that can be reached without any outside interaction and are part of the so called ϵ -closure(v) of a state v .

Definition 2.7.1. *Given an IA P and a state $v \in V_P$, we define the set ϵ -closure $_P(v)$ to be the smallest set U such that $v \in U$ and $u \in U \wedge (u, a, u') \in \mathcal{T}_P \wedge a \in \mathcal{A}_P^H \implies u' \in U$.*

This means that the ϵ -closure(v) contains at least the state v itself and all states which can be reached from v via only hidden actions. With this, we now have a tool to tackle the issue that if an IA is currently in a state v , the outside observer cannot distinguish between the states inside the ϵ -closure(v). We can now define the following.

Definition 2.7.2. *Let P be an IA and $v \in V_P$. We define*

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ExtEn}_P^I(v) &:= \{ a \mid \forall u \in \epsilon\text{-closure}(v) : a \in \mathcal{A}_P^I(u) \} \text{ and} \\ \text{ExtEn}_P^O(v) &:= \{ a \mid \exists u \in \epsilon\text{-closure}(v) : a \in \mathcal{A}_P^O(u) \}. \end{aligned}$$

This means that we define sets for all externally enabled input and output actions, which consider all input actions that are accepted in the ϵ -closure of the current state and all output actions that might be issued in any of the states inside the ϵ -closure. This enables us to define the following.

Definition 2.7.3. *Let P be an IA, $v \in V_P$, and $a \in \text{ExtEn}_P^I(v) \cup \text{ExtEn}_P^O(v)$. We define*

$$\text{ExtDest}_P(v, a) := \{ u' \mid (u, a, u') \in \mathcal{T}_P \wedge u \in \epsilon\text{-closure}(v) \}.$$

This concept corresponds to all states that can be reached from the ϵ -closure when an externally enabled action is issued, which corresponds to a view onto the IA from the outside.

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With this, we can define alternating simulations and then refinement of IAs.

Definition 2.7.4. Let P and Q be IAs and $\succeq \subseteq V_P \times V_Q$. We call \succeq an alternating simulation from Q to P if $\forall v \in V_P \forall u \in V_Q$:

$$\text{ExtEn}_P^I(v) \subseteq \text{ExtEn}_Q^I(u) \wedge \text{ExtEn}_Q^O \subseteq \text{ExtEn}_P^O(v) \text{ and} \quad (2.5)$$

$$\forall a \in \text{ExtEn}_P^I(v) \cup \text{ExtEn}_Q^O(u) : \quad (2.6)$$

$$\forall u' \in \text{ExtDest}_Q(u, a) : \exists v' \in \text{ExtDest}_P(v, a) : v' \succeq u'.$$

This formalism can be used to find whether or not an IA P can exhibit the same behaviour as another IA Q , in the sense that one can simulate P 's behaviour with Q .

Definition 2.7.5. Let P and Q be IAs. We say that P is refined by Q and write $P \succeq Q$ if

$$\mathcal{A}_P^I \subseteq \mathcal{A}_Q^I \wedge \mathcal{A}_P^O \supseteq \mathcal{A}_Q^O \text{ and}$$

$$\text{there exists an alternating simulation } \succeq \subseteq V_P \times V_Q \text{ s.t. } \exists v \in V_P^{\text{init}} u \in V_Q^{\text{init}} : v \succeq u.$$

This means that an IA P can only refine an IA Q if it does not issue any additional output actions and accepts at least the same input actions. The alternating simulation ensures that the behaviour of Q can be expressed in P . These formalism will be needed to define the approach to verify networks of FBs.

2.8 Extensions of Interface Automata

Since [2] forms the foundation for numerous extensions and abstractions and has been cited hundreds of times, it is impossible to cover all of this work. However, within the context of IEC 61499 and this thesis, the following is particularly relevant. In [3], Prähofer builds upon the foundation layed by de Alfaro and Henzinger. He introduces Hierarchical Automaton, which can be thought of as IAs with subcomponents. They act as the top-layer, orchestrating their subcomponents, which are modelled as IAs. In short, the hidden actions of an IA have been replaced with a set of subcomponents, forcing the Hierarchical Automaton to "outsource" its internal behaviour to subcomponents and

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therefore creates a hierarchical structure. He then also introduces the notion of external behavioural equivalence, by which one can check whether or not two IAs exhibit the same behaviour from the outside, i.e., they accept the same sequences of events. Overall, he uses the formalisms and concepts defined by [2] and extends them to describe and verify the behaviour of Hierarchical Automata. By introducing Hierarchical Abstraction, he is able to systematically create an externally behaviourally equivalent IA that is an accurate representation of the observable behaviour of the original.

In [4], Prähofer and Zoitl integrate this approach with the IEC 61499 Standard to verify these hierarchical structures. In contrast, this thesis focuses on arbitrary networks of FBs at a fixed layer of abstraction.

3 Modelling Function Blocks with Interface Automata

In this chapter, we will use the tools developed in Chapter 2 to model and analyse networks of FBs. We will assume to be given an IA that exhibits the same functionality as its corresponding FB. This approach enables formal verification of whether a network of FBs might encounter errors due to unintended interactions among them. We begin by modelling a single FB and continue with a more complex example to illustrate the process. Then, we will show that this method can be generally applied to networks of FBs if their corresponding IAs are given. Finally, we will discuss error states in more detail and then present the final verification approach.

3.1 Modelling a Single Function Block

Consider a very simple FB F depicted in Figure 3.1 with the following functionality: For every two input events in , F issues an output event out .

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Figure 3.1: Function Block F with input action in and output action out

We can describe its functionality with a very simple IA P .

$$\begin{aligned} P : \quad & V_P = \{1, 2, 3\}, \\ & V_P^{\text{init}} = \{1\}, \\ & \mathcal{A}_P^I = \{\text{in}\}, \\ & \mathcal{A}_P^O = \{\text{out}\}, \\ & \mathcal{A}_P^H = \emptyset, \\ & \mathcal{T}_P = \{(1, \text{in}, 2), (2, \text{in}, 3), (3, \text{out}, 1)\}. \end{aligned}$$

A graph of P could look like Figure 3.2.

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Figure 3.2: Graph of Interface Automaton P corresponding to Function Block F

As seen in the formal definition, we map the inputs of F onto the input actions of P and the outputs of F onto the output actions of P . Because we are only interested in the behaviour of the FB from an outside perspective, our FBs will not have any hidden actions. Hidden actions will become relevant when looking at the composition of IAs, because this process leads to the overlapping input and output actions of the IAs becoming hidden actions of the composition.

For simple behaviour like in this example, the corresponding IA P of F is easily derived. This is generally not true for FBs with more complex behaviour. In [4], Prähofer and Zoitl use service sequences to derive the IA from an FB. Service sequences are sequences of possible events. One can choose a set of such sequences that represent the behaviour of the FB in the best way possible. From this set, one can construct an IA that accepts the same chains of events. Building upon this approach or finding entirely new ways to derive IAs from FBs is not part of this thesis.

We now take a look at possible environments for F . The simplest one is the trivial environment which simply accepts all outputs and does not issue any inputs. We can think of the environment as another FBs inside the network, as shown in Figure 3.3.

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Figure 3.3: Function Block F with trivial Environment E depicted as an additional Function Block in the network

We only require that, as already stated in the previous chapter, the environment accepts all outputs of the (network of) FBs. On the contrary, it does not need to issue output actions, meaning that input ports of an FB can be left open. Since we consider the environment as the outermost layer, we assume that any open input ports of the network's FBs are not used by the environment or any other FB in the network.

A good way to think about the behaviour of a network in general is to view the output actions as the ones that are issued by the FB, as they are, for example, the actions that the environment feeds into the network of FBs, or which actions an FB can send to the ones its outputs are connected to. Conversely, the input actions describe if it is possible for an FB to receive or handle a certain action and also if this FB is accepting this specific action in its current state.

A graph of a possible environment E for P could look like in Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4: Graph of Interface Automaton E of trivial environment for Interface Automaton P

Formally, we define $E = (V_E = \{a\}, V_E^{init} = \{a\}, \mathcal{A}_E^I = \{out\}, \mathcal{A}_E^O = \mathcal{A}_E^H = \emptyset, \mathcal{T}_E = \{(a, out, a)\})$. This means that the environment consists of one state a , one input action out , no output or hidden actions, and one possible transition. Because this IA does not

3 Modelling Function Blocks with Interface Automata

have any enabled output actions, it never feeds anything into the system we are looking at, which is the single function block F from above. We can now formally check if the FB would work with this given environment.

First, we create the product automaton $E \otimes P$ as seen in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5: Product $P \otimes E$ of Interface Automaton P and the trivial environment E

Note that out is now a hidden action, as it connects P to E , while in remains an input action in the product $P \otimes E$. From the graph, one can already see that for any final composition of IAs, i.e., the last step after which no more IAs are added to the network, all vertices that are only reachable from the initial states via input actions will never be reached. This corresponds to input ports of FBs being left open.

We now check which of the states are actually reachable. In this case, our starting state is $1a \in V_P \times V_E$, as $1 \in V_P^{init}$ and $a \in V_E^{init}$ are the only starting states of P and E . In this state, P cannot issue any output actions, as its only output action out can be solely issued in state 3. This means that, for anything to happen, P needs input from the environment E . Because the environment E also cannot issue any output action, the result of reachable states is simply the state $1a$, as depicted in Figure 3.6.

Figure 3.6: Reachable states in $P \otimes E$ with initial state $1a$

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This shows that there are no reachable error states, as the only reachable state is $1a$, which itself is not an error state. Hence, the environment E is in fact a legal environment for the IA P , meaning that if the FB F is used in the same way as the environment IA E uses the IA P , the FB is used as intended. Let us now take a look at an example that leads to an error state.

This time, we use another very simple environment $E^* = (V_E = \{a\}, V_E^{init} = \{a\}, \mathcal{A}_E^I = \{out\}, \mathcal{A}_E^O = \{in\}, \mathcal{A}_E^O = \emptyset, \mathcal{T}_E = \{(a, in, a), (a, out, a)\})$. The only difference to the other environment E is that E^* also issues the output action in . A graph for E^* is depicted in Figure 3.7.

Figure 3.7: Graph of Interface Automaton of environment E^* for Interface Automaton P

As seen in Figure 3.8, the product for $P \otimes E^*$ looks almost identical. The only difference is that now in is also a hidden action, as it is issued by the environment E^* .

Figure 3.8: Product Automaton $P \otimes E^*$ that leads to reachable highlighted error state $3a$

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This results in an error state, because in 3a, the joint action $in \in \mathcal{A}_{E^*} \cap \mathcal{A}_P$ is an enabled output action of E^* , meaning $in \in \mathcal{A}_{E^*}^O(a)$, but not an enabled input action in the current state of P , because $in \notin \mathcal{A}_P^I(3)$, which is precisely the definition of an error state. Note that in the product, the actions that lead to error states are not actually depicted in the error state (in this case in in 3a). As this error state is reachable from the initial state $1a$, the environment E^* is invalid and might lead to errors. As a result, we can conclude that if the FB F is used the same way the environment IA E^* uses the IA P , errors might occur and F might not be used as intended.

3.2 Modelling a Function Block Network

When modelling a network of FBs, we will again assume the IA corresponding to the FBs we are modelling are given. Technically, we already looked at networks of FBs in Section 3.1, because the environment is just another IA with special constraints. Because of that, we now consider a network of three FBs F_A, F_B, F_C from Figure 3.9. First, we will compute the composition based on this example and then discuss the formal approach.

Figure 3.9: Network of Function Blocks $F_A, F_B,$ and F_C with input $start_A$ and output $true$ or $false$

The functionality of this network can be described as follows. When the $start_A$ action is triggered, F_A starts an internal check, resulting in either $pass_A$ or $fail_A$. If $pass_A$ is issued, F_B also runs an internal check that results in either $pass_B$ or $fail_B$. If both A and B pass, F_C will issue $true$. Otherwise, if either $fail_A$ or $fail_B$ is issued, F_C returns $false$.

We start by formally defining the corresponding IAs. Let A be the IA for the FB F_A , B for F_B , and C for F_C , formally described below.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 A : \quad & V_A = \{\text{Idle}_A, \text{Working}_A\}, \\
 & V_A^{\text{init}} = \{\text{Idle}_A\}, \\
 & \mathcal{A}_A^I = \{\text{start}_A\}, \\
 & \mathcal{A}_A^O = \{\text{pass}_A, \text{fail}_A\}, \\
 & \mathcal{A}_A^H = \emptyset, \\
 & \mathcal{T}_A = \{(\text{Idle}_A, \text{start}_A, \text{Working}_A), \\
 & \quad (\text{Working}_A, \text{pass}_A, \text{Idle}_A), \\
 & \quad (\text{Working}_A, \text{fail}_A, \text{Idle}_A)\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 B : \quad & V_B = \{\text{Idle}_B, \text{Working}_B\}, \\
 & V_B^{\text{init}} = \{\text{Idle}_B\}, \\
 & \mathcal{A}_B^I = \{\text{pass}_A\}, \\
 & \mathcal{A}_B^O = \{\text{pass}_B, \text{fail}_B\}, \\
 & \mathcal{A}_B^H = \emptyset, \\
 & \mathcal{T}_B = \{(\text{Idle}_B, \text{pass}_A, \text{Working}_B), \\
 & \quad (\text{Working}_B, \text{pass}_B, \text{Idle}_B), \\
 & \quad (\text{Working}_B, \text{fail}_B, \text{Idle}_B)\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 C : \quad & V_C = \{\text{Idle}_C, \text{Fail}, \text{Successful}\}, \\
 & V_C^{\text{init}} = \{\text{Idle}_C\}, \\
 & \mathcal{A}_C^I = \{\text{pass}_B\}, \\
 & \mathcal{A}_C^O = \{\text{true}, \text{false}\}, \\
 & \mathcal{A}_C^H = \emptyset, \\
 & \mathcal{T}_C = \{(\text{Idle}_C, \text{pass}_B, \text{Successful}), \\
 & \quad (\text{Idle}_C, \text{fail}_A, \text{Fail}), \\
 & \quad (\text{Idle}_C, \text{fail}_B, \text{Fail}), \\
 & \quad (\text{Successful}, \text{true}, \text{Idle}_C), \\
 & \quad (\text{Fail}, \text{false}, \text{Idle}_C)\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

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The graphs of the IAs are depicted in Figure 3.10.

Figure 3.10: Graphs of the Interface Automata *A*, *B*, and *C*

As a next step, we will compute the product $A \otimes B$. This can easily be done by simply following Definition 2.3.2. We obtain the following result and the corresponding graph is depicted in Figure 3.11.

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$$\begin{aligned}
A \otimes B : \quad & V_{A \otimes B} = V_A \times V_B, \\
& V_{A \otimes B}^{\text{init}} = \{ (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B) \}, \\
& \mathcal{A}_{A \otimes B}^I = \{ \text{start}_A \}, \\
& \mathcal{A}_{A \otimes B}^O = \{ \text{fail}_A, \text{pass}_B, \text{fail}_B \}, \\
& \mathcal{A}_{A \otimes B}^H = \{ \text{pass}_A \}, \\
& \mathcal{T}_{A \otimes B} = \{ ((\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B), \text{start}_A, (\text{Working}_A, \text{Idle}_B)), \\
& \quad ((\text{Working}_A, \text{Idle}_B), \text{fail}_A, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B)), \\
& \quad ((\text{Working}_A, \text{Idle}_B), \text{pass}_A, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Working}_B)), \\
& \quad ((\text{Idle}_A, \text{Working}_B), \text{fail}_B, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B)), \\
& \quad ((\text{Idle}_A, \text{Working}_B), \text{pass}_B, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B)), \\
& \quad ((\text{Idle}_A, \text{Working}_B), \text{start}_A, (\text{Working}_A, \text{Working}_B)), \\
& \quad ((\text{Working}_A, \text{Working}_B), \text{pass}_A, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Working}_B)), \\
& \quad ((\text{Working}_A, \text{Working}_B), \text{fail}_A, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Working}_B)), \\
& \quad ((\text{Working}_A, \text{Working}_B), \text{pass}_B, (\text{Working}_A, \text{Idle}_B)), \\
& \quad ((\text{Working}_A, \text{Working}_B), \text{fail}_B, (\text{Working}_A, \text{Idle}_B)) \}.
\end{aligned}$$

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Figure 3.11: Product $A \otimes B$ with highlighted error state

Now, one can remove all unreachable states together with all transitions that involve them. In this case, there are no unreachable states. After that, one can compute the set of error states in $A \otimes B$. This can be done by simply checking for every state if it meets the conditions of an error state. In this case, we find that $Working_A, Working_B$ is an error state due to the shared action $pass_A$ in $A \otimes B$, since $pass_A$ might be issued in $Working_A \in V_A$, while B would not accept it. This makes intuitive sense, as there is no queue and A and B can each process only one event at a time.

We now use Algorithm 1 to compute all states from which this error state could be reached only using the output and hidden actions of $A \otimes B$. We start by setting $U_0 \leftarrow Illegal(A, B) = \{(Working_A, Working_B)\}$ and $k \leftarrow 0$. To compute $U_{k+1} = U_1$, we need to compute $OHpre_{A \otimes B}(U_0)$, as defined in Definition 2.6.2. Because the only error state in U_0 can only be reached via input action $start_A$ of $A \otimes B$, we can directly conclude that

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$U_1 = U_0$. This ends the loop and returns the compatible states $Cmp(A, B) = V_{A \otimes B} \setminus U_0 = V_{A \otimes B} \setminus \{ (Working_A, Working_B) \}$.

This results in the graph in Figure 3.12 and is formally defined below.

$$\begin{aligned}
 A \parallel B : \quad & V_{A \parallel B} = Cmp(A, B) = V_{A \otimes B} \setminus \{ (Working_A, Working_B) \}, \\
 & V_{A \parallel B}^{init} = \{ (Idle_A, Idle_B) \}, \\
 & \mathcal{A}_{A \parallel B}^I = \{ start_A \}, \\
 & \mathcal{A}_{A \parallel B}^O = \{ pass_B, fail_B \}, \\
 & \mathcal{A}_{A \parallel B}^H = \{ pass_A \}, \\
 & \mathcal{T}_{A \parallel B} = \{ ((Idle_A, Idle_B), start_A, (Working_A, Idle_B)), \\
 & \quad ((Working_A, Idle_B), fail_A, (Idle_A, Idle_B)), \\
 & \quad ((Working_A, Idle_B), pass_A, (Idle_A, Working_B)), \\
 & \quad ((Idle_A, Working_B), fail_B, (Idle_A, Idle_B)), \\
 & \quad ((Idle_A, Working_B), pass_B, (Idle_A, Idle_B)) \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

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Figure 3.12: Composition $A||B$

From this, one can already see that A and B are in fact compatible, as $V_{A||B} \neq \emptyset$. We imposed a constraint for possible environments (or other IAs in the network), specifically to not issue input action $start_A$ when $A||B$ is in the state $Idle_A, Working_B$.

The next step is to repeat the action and now compute the composition $(A||B)||C$. First, we again compute $(A||B) \otimes C$, which can be seen in Figure 3.13 and is formally defined as follows.

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$(A||B) \otimes C$:

$$V_{A||B} \otimes C = V_{A||B} \times V_C,$$

$$V_{A||B}^{\text{init}} = \{ (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Idle}_C) \},$$

$$\mathcal{A}_{(A||B) \otimes C}^I = \{ \text{start}_A \},$$

$$\mathcal{A}_{(A||B) \otimes C}^O = \{ \text{true}, \text{false} \},$$

$$\mathcal{A}_{(A||B) \otimes C}^H = \{ \text{pass}_A, \text{fail}_A, \text{pass}_B, \text{fail}_B \},$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_{(A||B) \otimes C} = \{ & ((\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Idle}_C), \text{start}_A, (\text{Working}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Idle}_C)), \\ & ((\text{Working}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Idle}_C), \text{fail}_A, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Failed})), \\ & ((\text{Working}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Idle}_C), \text{pass}_A, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Working}_B, \text{Idle}_C)), \\ & ((\text{Idle}_A, \text{Working}_B, \text{Idle}_C), \text{fail}_B, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Failed})), \\ & ((\text{Idle}_A, \text{Working}_B, \text{Idle}_C), \text{pass}_B, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Successful})), \\ & ((\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Successful}), \text{true}, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Idle}_C)), \\ & ((\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Failed}), \text{false}, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Idle}_C)), \\ & ((\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Successful}), \text{start}, (\text{Working}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Successful})), \\ & ((\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Failed}), \text{start}, (\text{Working}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Failed})), \\ & ((\text{Working}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Successful}), \text{pass}_A, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Working}_B, \text{Successful})), \\ & ((\text{Working}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Successful}), \text{true}, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Idle}_C)), \\ & ((\text{Working}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Failed}), \text{pass}_A, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Working}_B, \text{Failed})), \\ & ((\text{Working}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Failed}), \text{false}, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Idle}_C)), \\ & ((\text{Idle}_A, \text{Working}_B, \text{Successful}), \text{true}, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Idle}_C)), \\ & ((\text{Idle}_A, \text{Working}_B, \text{Failed}), \text{false}, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Idle}_C)) \}. \end{aligned}$$

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Figure 3.13: Product $(A||B) \otimes C$ with highlighted error states

Again, we check for error states. In this case, the joint actions are $\mathcal{A}_{A||B} \cap \mathcal{A}_C = \{failA, failB, passB\}$. Hence, we check all states in which those actions are enabled output actions, meaning we iterate over all $(v, u) \in V_{(A||B) \otimes C}$ with $\exists a \in \mathcal{A}_{A||B} \cap \mathcal{A}_C : a \in \mathcal{A}_{(A||B)}^O(v) \vee a \in \mathcal{A}_C^O(u)$. By looking at the error states, one can see that they correspond to the fact that the system needs to wait for C to return either *true* or *false* before starting again.

We now use Algorithm 1 again to compute its compatible states and arrive at the composition below, whose graph is depicted in Figure 3.14.

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$(A||B)||C$:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cmp}(A||B, C) = V_{A||B} \times V_C \setminus \{ & (\text{Working}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Successful}), \\ & (\text{Working}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Failed}), (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Working}_B, \text{Successful}), \\ & (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Working}_B, \text{Failed}) \}, \end{aligned}$$

$$V_{A||B}^{\text{init}} = \{ (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Idle}_C) \},$$

$$\mathcal{A}_{(A||B) \otimes C}^I = \{ \text{start}_A \},$$

$$\mathcal{A}_{(A||B) \otimes C}^O = \{ \text{true}, \text{false} \},$$

$$\mathcal{A}_{(A||B) \otimes C}^H = \{ \text{pass}_A, \text{fail}_A, \text{pass}_B, \text{fail}_B \},$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_{(A||B) \otimes C} = \{ & ((\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Idle}_C), \text{start}_A, (\text{Working}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Idle}_C)), \\ & ((\text{Working}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Idle}_C), \text{fail}_A, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Failed})), \\ & ((\text{Working}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Idle}_C), \text{pass}_A, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Working}_B, \text{Idle}_C)), \\ & ((\text{Idle}_A, \text{Working}_B, \text{Idle}_C), \text{fail}_B, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Failed})), \\ & ((\text{Idle}_A, \text{Working}_B, \text{Idle}_C), \text{pass}_B, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Successful})), \\ & ((\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Successful}), \text{true}, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Idle}_C)), \\ & ((\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Failed}), \text{false}, (\text{Idle}_A, \text{Idle}_B, \text{Idle}_C)) \}. \end{aligned}$$

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Figure 3.14: Final composition $A||B||C$

From $A||B||C$, one can see that the network of FBs can in fact be used like in Figure 3.9. The composition also provides a general overview of the network, highlighting all valid actions and sequences of events. As $A||B||C$ is not a closed IAs, one could now check it against given environments.

3.3 Formalisation and Generic Approach

After understanding how to compute the composition of IAs, we will now show that this actually corresponds to verifying networks of FBs. We will start by defining what is meant by network of FBs and that modelling such networks with sets of IAs works as intended. For this we use a limited version of FBs, i.e., we fully omit data connections.

Definition 3.3.1. Let \mathcal{F} be a set of FBs and $F \in \mathcal{F}$. Then, the event inputs of F are numbered $1, \dots, N_F^I$ and the event outputs $N_F^I + 1, \dots, N_F^O$.

We call $c := ((F_i, k), (F_j, n)) \in (\mathcal{F} \times \mathbb{N})^2$ a connection on \mathcal{F} if $k \leq N_{F_i}^O$ and $n \leq N_{F_j}^I$.

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A tuple $(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{C})$ for a set of FBs \mathcal{F} and a set of connections \mathcal{C} is called a network, if

$$\forall ((F_i, k), (F_j, n)) \in \mathcal{C} : i = j \implies n \neq k \text{ and} \quad (3.1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \forall ((F_i, k), (F_j, n)) \in \mathcal{C} : 1 \leq k \leq N_{F_i}^I \wedge N_{F_j}^I < n \leq N_{F_j}^O \vee \\ N_{F_i}^I < k \leq N_{F_i}^O \wedge 1 \leq n \leq N_{F_j}^I. \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

We say an IA A corresponds to an FB F if

$$\exists h : \underline{N}_F^O \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_A \text{ with } h(\underline{N}_F^I) = \mathcal{A}_A^I \wedge h(\underline{N}_F^O \setminus \underline{N}_F^I) = \mathcal{A}_A^O, \quad (3.3)$$

$$\mathcal{A}_A^H = \emptyset, \text{ and} \quad (3.4)$$

$$h \text{ is bijective.} \quad (3.5)$$

The IA also needs to match the FB's functionality, but this is not relevant for the composition and is assumed in this thesis.

We say a set \mathcal{S} of IAs corresponds to a network $(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{C})$ if

every IA corresponds to exactly one FB and

$$\begin{aligned} \forall k, n \in \mathbb{N} \forall F_i, F_j \in \mathcal{F} : ((F_i, k), (F_j, n)) \in \mathcal{C} \iff h_{F_i}(k) = h_{F_j}(n) \forall i \neq j \\ \text{with } h_{F_i}, h_{F_j} \text{ being the correspondence functions.} \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 1. Let \mathcal{S} be a set of IAs corresponding to a network $(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{C})$. Then, $\forall A_i, A_j \in \mathcal{S} : A_i$ is composable with A_j for $i \neq j$.

Proof. Let $(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{C})$ be a network of FBs and \mathcal{S} their corresponding set of IAs. To show that all A_i, A_j are composable for $i \neq j$, we can show without loss of generality that A_1 is composable with every A_i for $i > 1$.

To find if A_1 is composable with some A_i , we need to check if

$$\underbrace{\mathcal{A}_{A_1}^H \cap \mathcal{A}_{A_i}}_{(1)} = \underbrace{\mathcal{A}_{A_i}^H \cap \mathcal{A}_{A_1}}_{(2)} = \underbrace{\mathcal{A}_{A_1}^I \cap \mathcal{A}_{A_i}^I}_{(3)} = \underbrace{\mathcal{A}_{A_1}^O \cap \mathcal{A}_{A_i}^O}_{(4)} = \emptyset$$

Because of equation 3.4 of our definition of corresponding IAs, we know that $\mathcal{A}_{A_1}^H = \mathcal{A}_{A_i}^H = \emptyset \implies (1)$ and (2) .

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We now assume that $\mathcal{A}_{A_1}^I \cap \mathcal{A}_{A_i}^I \neq \emptyset$ and prove (3) by contradiction. Let $a \in \mathcal{A}_{A_1}^I \cap \mathcal{A}_{A_i}^I$. Then, $\exists k \in \underline{N_{F_1}^I} \setminus \underline{N_{F_i}^I} \ n \in \underline{N_{F_i}^I} : h_{F_1}(k) = h_{F_i}(n)$, hence $((F_1, k), (F_i, n)) \in \mathcal{C}$ for such k, n . But this is in contradiction to $(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{C})$ being a network, as it violates equation 3.2. Hence, (3) must hold.

The proof of (4) is similar. We assume that $\mathcal{A}_{A_1}^O \cap \mathcal{A}_{A_i}^O \neq \emptyset$. Let $a \in \mathcal{A}_{A_1}^O$. Then, as above, $\exists k \in \underline{N_{F_1}^O} \setminus \underline{N_{F_i}^O} \ n \in \underline{N_{F_i}^O} \setminus \underline{N_{F_i}^I} : h_{F_1}(k) = h_{F_i}(n)$, hence $((F_1, k), (F_i, n)) \in \mathcal{C}$ for such k, n , which, again, violates equation 3.2. Thus, (4) must hold. \square

Theorem 2. *Every set of IAs \mathcal{S} corresponding to a network $(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{C})$ can always be composed in arbitrary order.*

From this, it also follows that the environment does not need to be the last IA that is composed.

Proof. Let $\mathcal{S} = \{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_k\}$ be a set of IAs corresponding to a network $(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{C})$. By Theorem 1, we know that the IAs of \mathcal{S} are pairwise composable. We proof this by induction on the number of already composed IAs n .

Let $n = 1$, then by Theorem 1, A_1 is composable with any other $A_i \in \mathcal{S}$.

$n \rightarrow n + 1 \leq k$.

Let $A_{\underline{n}} = (A_1 || A_2) || A_3 || \dots || A_n$. We show that $A_{\underline{n}}$ is composable with A_{n+1} . In order to do that, we need to show

$$\underbrace{\mathcal{A}_{A_{n+1}}^H \cap \mathcal{A}_{A_{\underline{n}}}}_{(1)} = \underbrace{\mathcal{A}_{A_{\underline{n}}}^H \cap \mathcal{A}_{A_{n+1}}}_{(2)} = \underbrace{\mathcal{A}_{A_{n+1}}^I \cap \mathcal{A}_{A_{\underline{n}}}^I}_{(3)} = \underbrace{\mathcal{A}_{A_{n+1}}^O \cap \mathcal{A}_{A_{\underline{n}}}^O}_{(4)} = \emptyset$$

1. Because of equation 3.4, we know that $\mathcal{A}_{A_{n+1}}^H = \emptyset \implies (1)$
2. From the definition of composition (Definition 2.6.3), it follows that

$$\mathcal{A}_{A_{\underline{n}}}^H = \bigcup_{i \in \underline{n}} \mathcal{A}_{A_i}^H \cup \bigcup_{i \in \underline{n-1}} \left(\bigcup_{k \in i} \mathcal{A}_{A_k} \cap \mathcal{A}_{A_{i+1}} \right).$$

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By definition, we know that

$$\forall i \in \underline{n} : \mathcal{A}_{A_i}^H \cap \mathcal{A}_{A_{n+1}} = \emptyset.$$

Thus, it follows that

$$\left(\bigcup_{i \in \underline{n}} \mathcal{A}_{A_i}^H \right) \cap \mathcal{A}_{A_{n+1}} = \emptyset.$$

It remains to show that

$$\mathcal{A}_{A_{n+1}} \cap \bigcup_{i \in \underline{n-1}} \left(\bigcup_{k \in i} \mathcal{A}_{A_k} \cap \mathcal{A}_{A_{i+1}} \right) = \emptyset.$$

We prove this by contradiction. Assume that

$$\mathcal{A}_{A_{n+1}} \cap \bigcup_{i \in \underline{n-1}} \left(\bigcup_{k \in i} \mathcal{A}_{A_k} \cap \mathcal{A}_{A_{i+1}} \right) \neq \emptyset,$$

then there exists $a \in \mathcal{A}_{A_{n+1}}$ such that

$$a \in \bigcup_{i \in \underline{n-1}} \left(\bigcup_{k \in i} \mathcal{A}_{A_k} \cap \mathcal{A}_{A_{i+1}} \right).$$

By unfolding this expression, we find

$$\exists i \in \underline{n-1} : a \in \bigcup_{k \in i} \mathcal{A}_{A_k} \cap \mathcal{A}_{A_{i+1}},$$

which implies

$$a \in \mathcal{A}_{A_{i+1}} \quad \text{and} \quad \exists k \in i : a \in \mathcal{A}_{A_k}.$$

Since $A_{n+1} \neq A_{i+1} \neq A_k$ for such i and k , the action a must be present in three different IAs, which leads to a contradiction: If $a \in \mathcal{A}_{A_{n+1}}^I$, then $a \in \mathcal{A}_{A_{i+1}}^O$. This

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implies that A_k is not composable with either A_{n+1} or A_{i+1} , which contradicts the fact that \mathcal{S} corresponds to a network.

3. We know that $\forall i \in \underline{n} : \mathcal{A}_{A_{n+1}}^I \cap \mathcal{A}_{A_i}^I = \emptyset$, hence $\mathcal{A}_{A_{n+1}}^I \cap \bigcup_{i \in \underline{n}} (\mathcal{A}_{A_i}^I) = \emptyset$ and thus $\mathcal{A}_{A_{n+1}}^I \cap \mathcal{A}_{A_{\underline{n}}}^I = \emptyset$, because $\mathcal{A}_{A_{\underline{n}}}^I \subseteq \bigcup_{i \in \underline{n}} \mathcal{A}_{A_i}^I$.

4. The proof for the fourth statement is analogous to the third.

□

We can now define an algorithm to verify a network of FBs in an environment.

Algorithm 2: Algorithm to verify a network of Function Blocks

Input: Set of Interface Automata $\mathcal{S} = \{S_1, \dots, S_n\}$ corresponding to a network $(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{C})$

Output: Non-empty composition $S_1 || S_2 || \dots || S_n$ or \emptyset

$k \leftarrow 2$;

$A \leftarrow S_1$;

while $k \leq n$ **do**

$A \leftarrow A || S_k$;

if $V_A == \emptyset$ **then**

return \emptyset ;

end

$k \leftarrow k + 1$;

end

return A ;

If the resulting $A_{\mathcal{S}}$ is closed and non-empty, it means that there remain no error states. If the resulting $A_{\mathcal{S}}$ is open, we can now check $A_{\mathcal{S}}$ against environments. Of course, this enables one to check when the issues arise and to obtain more detailed output than just the composition or \emptyset .

3.4 Different Types of Error States

If an error state is detected, we can now look into more detail on what kind of error state it is. By looking at different cases we can analyse their consequences and create a more flexible model for composition.

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Let P, Q be composable IAs and $(v, u) \in V_{P \otimes Q}$ be an error state, which means that $\exists a \in \mathcal{A}_P \cap \mathcal{A}_Q : a \in \mathcal{A}_P^O(v) \wedge a \notin \mathcal{A}_Q^I(u) \vee a \in \mathcal{A}_P^I(v) \wedge a \notin \mathcal{A}_Q^O$.

This can be viewed as the output of one IA being ignored by the other. This is not necessarily an error in the usual sense, but in the context of FB networks often even desired behaviour, motivating the following definition.

Definition 3.4.1. Let $P \otimes Q$ be the product of two IAs P and Q and $(v, u) \in V_{P \otimes Q}$ an error state, such that $a \in \mathcal{A}_P \cap \mathcal{A}_Q : a \in \mathcal{A}_P^O(v) \wedge a \notin \mathcal{A}_Q^I(u)$. We call Q' extended with action a at state u by adding a self loop to Q , meaning $\mathcal{T}_{Q'} = \mathcal{T}_Q \cup (u, a, u)$.

Here, we formalise the idea of ignoring inputs. Now, the extended Q' and the extended product $P \otimes Q'$ accept the previously not accepted input, while effectively ignoring it. With this, we can also expand upon the notion of error states and can call them potentially ignored input state. If $\bigcup_{v' \in \epsilon\text{-closure}(v)} \mathcal{A}_P^I(v') \cap \mathcal{A}_Q^O(v') = \mathcal{A}_Q^I(v') \cap \mathcal{A}_P^O(v') = \emptyset$, we call it an ignored input state. For IAs P_F that model single FBs, we assume them to not have hidden actions, meaning that potentially ignored input states are always ignored input states. We can now show that extending an IA simply refines it, i.e., not limiting its original behaviour.

Theorem 3. Let P and P' be IAs and P' be P extended by action a at state v . Then, $P \succeq P'$

Proof. Let P be an IA, $v \in V_P$, and $a \in \mathcal{A}_P^I : a \notin \mathcal{A}_P(v)$. Let Q be P extended by a in v . Since the states of P and Q do not differ, we denote states in Q with v' . First, we need to show that $\mathcal{A}_P^O \subseteq \mathcal{A}_Q^O \wedge \mathcal{A}_Q^I \subseteq \mathcal{A}_P^I$, which follows directly.

Second, we need to show that there exists an alternating simulation from Q to P and (in this case) only $v \succeq v'$ for $v' \in V_Q$ being the extended state in Q .

Equation 2.5 from Definition 2.7.4 follows directly. For equation 2.6, we know that P and Q only differ in one transition, namely (v, a, v) . Because $a \notin \mathcal{A}_P(v) \implies a \notin \text{ExtEn}_P^I(v)$ and $a \notin \mathcal{A}_Q^O \implies a \notin \text{ExtEn}_Q^O(v)$ the equation holds, because there clearly exists an alternating simulation from P to P , hence $P \succeq Q$.

□

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One specific case is interesting: By adding (v', a, v') , the action a might be added to $ExtEn_Q^I(v^*)$, for $v^* \in \epsilon - closure(v')$. But because this happens in Q and for the definition of an alternating simulation we only look at $ExtEn_Q^O(v')$, this does not matter for refinement.

If we now compute the composition of two IAs P and Q and find an error state, we can decide to simply extend P or Q to remove it. Then, we can replace Q by the extended version and with Theorem 3, we know we can do this without losing any functionality. Because when computing the composition not only the error states themselves, but all states from which they are reachable via hidden or output actions are removed, one needs to fix all such states too, as otherwise the extended state would be removed regardless.

Consider the following IAs A and B and their composition in Figure 3.15.

Figure 3.15: Product of A and B with highlighted error state and without unreachable states

The error arises because B does not accept the joint action $link$ as an input action in state b . One can now decide that ignoring the input from A in B at state b is actually intended. Thus, we now extend B by adding the transition $(b, link, b)$.

Figure 3.16: Product of A and extended B with highlighted extension and without unreachable states

Figure 3.16 now shows the product of A with the extended version of B .

3.5 Deadlock States

There are also other kinds of states that are potentially malicious. Assume $(\mathcal{A}_P^O \cup \mathcal{A}_P^H) \cap \mathcal{A}_Q(u) = \emptyset$. Then, we call $(v, u) \in V_{P||Q}$ an execution deadlock state. An execution deadlock is a state at which no changes can happen any more, meaning no state changes will happen as both IAs are waiting for input. Looking at FBs, an execution deadlock is a point at which nothing observable happens anymore. We can define a more general deadlock case: If $\bigcup_{v' \in \epsilon\text{-closure}(v)} \mathcal{A}_P^O(v') = \bigcup_{u' \in \epsilon\text{-closure}(u)} \mathcal{A}_Q^O(u') = \emptyset$, we call (v, u) an interaction deadlock state. In such a state, no interaction between FBs can happen any more, but changes inside FBs might still take place.

Formally speaking, a deadlock state is not an error state. This becomes evident by looking at an IA $P||Q$ that is intended to terminate after some finite number of steps. Then, clearly, neither output nor hidden actions need to be enabled after reaching some final state. Because networks of FBs are often used for cyclic execution without a defined endpoint, it is worth considering such states. We regard deadlock states that occur in compositions of non-extended IAs as intended deadlock states, e.g. terminating a process. Now, if error states occur, the system enters a state after which it cannot guarantee correct execution anymore, as the output of one component might have been wrongfully ignored. If one

now extends an IA to ignore an error state, it gains behavioural freedom, which might lead to new deadlock states.

3.6 Proposed Algorithm

Given the notion of extending IAs described above, we can adapt Algorithm 2 into Algorithm 3. We propose this as a formalised approach to verify networks of FBs.

Algorithm 3: Extended algorithm to verify a network of Function Blocks

Input: Set of Interface Automata $\mathcal{S} = \{S_1, \dots, S_n\}$ corresponding to a network $(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{C})$

Output: Non-empty, potentially extended composition $S_1 || S_2 || \dots || S_n$ or \emptyset

$k \leftarrow 2$;

$A \leftarrow S_1 \in \mathcal{S}$;

while $k \leq n$ **do**

foreach $(e, e') \in \text{Illegal}(A, S_k)$ **do**

$a = \text{conflictingAction}(e)$; // The joint action causing the error

if $\text{isMalicious}((e, e'))$ **then**

if $\text{issuedBy}(a) == A$ **then**

$\mathcal{T}_A = \mathcal{T}_A \cup (e, a, e)$; // Extend A

end

else

$\mathcal{T}_{S_k} = \mathcal{T}_{S_k} \cup (e', a, e')$; // Extend S_k

end

end

end

if $V_A == \emptyset$ **then**

return \emptyset

end

$A \leftarrow A || S_k$;

$k \leftarrow k + 1$;

end

return A ;

In order to employ Algorithm 3, one needs to decide either manually or define a function $\text{isMalicious}(\text{errorState})$ to decide whether or not a given error state should be ignored and the respective IA be extended. With this, we have refined the composition to account

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for intentionally ignored inputs, which makes it specifically tailored to the verification of FB networks.

4 Evaluation with a Use Case

The theory developed earlier can now be applied to analyse part of a practical example: the Capping Station [7]. The Capping Station is a model of a real-world automation system and has been used for example to demonstrate the use of Eclipse 4diac™ [8] and concrete implementations of the IEC 61499 Standard [5]. We will use an adapted version of this example to show a real-world application for the approach presented in this work.

4.1 Modelling the Capping Station

The functionality of the Capping Station is to place an upper part onto a lower part, which is transported on a conveyor belt. For simplicity, we focus only on the conveyor belt part. We model the entry and exit of lower parts at the Capping Station, ensuring only one lower part is inside at any given time. We then want to let a part enter as soon as the Capping Station is free and exit as soon as capping is complete. When a lower part is waiting in front of the Capping Station, we retrieve a signal from a sensor, as well as when a part has fully entered. Similarly, a signal is retrieved for a part being completely inside the Capping Station or leaving. We use those signals to provide the desired functionality. The FB network of the modelled part of the Capping Station is depicted in Figure 4.1.

4 Evaluation with a Use Case

Figure 4.1: Function Block network of the adapted part of the Capping Station including a Function Block to model the environment

The following points provide additional context regarding Figure 4.1.

- *InletStopper1* and *InletStopper2* are the same type of FB, hence they issue and accept the exact same events. In order for the corresponding IAs being correctly defined, their actions differ in the number appended to clearly map input ports to output ports.
- The information provided by the sensors is modelled with *InletStopper1* and *InletStopper2* and causes their output events.
- *Free* stores the current status, specifying whether or not the Capping Station is occupied at the moment. It functions similarly to a Flip-Flop, either setting the state to occupied or restoring it to free. In its IA equivalent, we model it stricter, accepting only alternating set and reset actions.

4 Evaluation with a Use Case

- The environment FB is highlighted as it is not an actual part of the FB network and we will not model it concretely. It is still included in Figure 4.1 to show which actions are controlled from outside the network and how one might model such a network with a concrete environment.

For real-world applications, it is important to note that the states of the FBs and therefore the IAs are not known at start time, hence an initialisation routine is needed to ensure each IA is in a proper starting state. As this would increase the complexity of the example even more, we omitted it here. One way to achieve this would be to simply add a *setup* action to every IA in the network with a connection from every state to an initial state of the IA. The environment could then simply issue this once at the very start to ensure a correct entry point. While this guarantees that the IAs are in the correct states, it does not ensure the real world is. To fully address this, one would need to find and execute a chain of setup actions.

The first step is to derive the IAs from the given FB network. The following are graphs of the IAs of the network. Due to the complexity and the fact that the formal definition can directly be derived from the graph depiction, only the graphs are provided for this example and not the full formal specifications. The initial states are given in the figure descriptions.

- Figure 4.2 shows the IA *Free*, which is used to store information on whether or not the Capping Station is free at the moment. It provides an output event for *Gate* if the occupation status changes.
- Figure 4.3 shows the IA *Index* which fixes and releases the current part. It also receives input from the environment on when it should release the part, i.e., when the capping process is finished. When modelling the full Capping Station, this input would most likely come from inside another part of the network. This component was not part of the original Capping Station in [7].
- Figure 4.4 shows the IA *Gate* which controls whether a new part can enter the Capping Station. It is responsible for letting a lower part inside the Capping Station and tracks whether another part attempts to enter while the current part is still in the process of entering or capping.

4 Evaluation with a Use Case

- Figure 4.5 shows the IA *InletStopper1* which provides information about parts waiting to enter the Capping Station via the sensors. *InletStopper2* is identical to *InletStopper1*, except that it uses actions and states postfix with 2 instead of 1. It provides information about parts exiting the Capping Station. We model a part having fully entered the Capping Station by *InletStopper2* issuing a *partW2* output action initiated by its sensor.

Figure 4.2: Graph of *Free* with initial state *IsFree*

4 Evaluation with a Use Case

Figure 4.3: Graph of *Index* with initial state *ReadyIndex*

Figure 4.4: Graph of *Gate* with initial state *Unblocked*

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Figure 4.5: Graph of *InletStopper1* with initial state *Ready1*

We can now verify whether the parts we modelled can be used together without producing errors. As one can see in Figure 4.1, the network can be divided into two components that are fairly independent: *Gate*, *Free*, *InletStopper1*, and *Index*, *InletStopper2*. We start by computing the product $Free \otimes Gate$ seen in Figure 4.6 and the composition in Figure 4.7. Because they are communicating via the action *switch*, it is now a hidden action of $Free || Gate$.

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Figure 4.6: Graph of $Free \otimes Gate$ with highlighted error states and without unreachable states

4 Evaluation with a Use Case

Figure 4.7: Graph of $Free||Gate$

Next, we compute the product $Free||Gate \otimes InletStopper1$. Because no error states arise, only the composition $Free||Gate||InletStopper1$ is shown in Figure 4.8.

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Figure 4.8: Graph of $Free||Gate||InletStopper1$

We continue with the other component and compute $Index||InletStopper2$ as seen in Figure 4.9. Again, we omit the product because no error states arise.

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Figure 4.9: Graph of $Index||InletStopper2$

Next, we compute $(Free||Gate||InletStopper1) \otimes (Index||InletStopper2)$ as seen in Figure 4.10 and the final composition $Free||Gate||InletStopper1||Index||InletStopper2$ in Figure 4.11.

Because in the last step of composition, the two combined components $Free||Gate||InletStopper1$ and $Index||InletStopper2$ are only connected via one action ($partE2$) and are acting relatively independent of each other, the size of the IA increases drastically, as most of all possible combinations are valid states of the network.

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Figure 4.10: Product $(Free || Gate || InletStopper1) \otimes (Index || InletStopper2)$ with highlighted error states

4 Evaluation with a Use Case

Figure 4.11: Final Composition (*Free*||*Gate*||*InletStopper1*||*Index*||*InletStopper2*)

4.2 Evaluation

Overall, the Capping Station example demonstrated that the presented approach can be employed in a real-world application of limited size. Since we did not assert that any error states model in fact desired behaviour, we effectively employed Algorithm 2. This leads to the following findings.

For combinations of IAs that allow only very specific sequences of events, computing the product and composition is a sensible approach. This became evident when composing *Index* and *InletStopper2*. In general, it implies that when two IAs issue many shared output actions but accept them as input actions in only a few states, it results in a significant reduction in the number of states in the composition due to pruning. The example also highlighted that networks with more independent behaviour are not well suited for this approach due to the state explosion problem, which was particularly noticeable in the final composition step of the Capping Station.

5 Conclusion

5.1 Summary

The original formalism of IAs remains a simple yet effective way to model the interaction of components of a network. As we have shown, it is especially useful to test small and strongly interacting networks of FBs, as the number of states generated during composition can vary significantly. This potential early pruning can show potential errors quickly and give an idea for when and why an interaction might fail.

We could show the correctness of the verification approach for networks of FBs without direct self loops and omitting data connections. This directly limits the applicability of the approach. While for boolean values it might still be feasible for some networks to simply extend the state space, for data types with domains larger than two elements, this could already lead to an unmanageable state explosion.

Furthermore, deriving an IA from a given FB is generally a non-trivial task, yet its correctness is critically important. One needs to make sure that the behaviour of the IAs accurately models that of the FBs, as otherwise the verification process has no basis. However, once a composition has been computed or an IA has been derived, it can be reused, thus shifting the workload to the initial derivation or computation phase.

Overall, the final approach presented in Algorithm 3 can be applied to real-world examples, as demonstrated in 4. However, it is important to recognise its limitations and suitable use cases, as discussed in Section 4.2.

5.2 Outlook

As this work presents a basic approach to verify networks of FBs using IAs, there are many directions to expand upon this. First, the approach could be extended to more general networks of FBs, allowing for data connections and direct self loops. Second, ways of modelling one output being fed into multiple input ports and vice versa, which would impact the assumption that all IAs are pairwise composable, could be explored. One possible approach to addressing this might be to impose an order on the composition process. Third, the usefulness of the presented notion of expanding IAs to model actively ignoring inputs could be evaluated and its real-world applicability demonstrated. Moreover, the possibility of eliminating or minimizing hidden actions during composition could be explored to focus on the verification of component interactions and mitigating the state explosion problem, which remains a significant limitation of the approach. Furthermore, ideas for modelling time constraints and concurrent actions might be considered. Overall, this shows that there are many ways to expand upon the presented formalisation and verification approach.

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